

a. Overall Scores

b. Environmental Scores

c. Economic Scores

d. Social Scores

Water Consumption

N Surplus

P Surplus

Land Use Change

Greenhouse Gas

Soil Erosion

Labor Productivity

Finance Access

Price Volatility

Government Support

Trade Openness

Food Loss

Crop Diversity

Food Affordability

Under-nourishment

Rural Poverty

Gender Gap

Land Right

